

GUANGDONG PRIVATE VOCATIONAL COLLEGE TEACHER'S DECISIONS TO UNDERTAKE POSTGRADUATE STUDY IN MALAYSIA

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Abstract

This study article's main goal is to look at the many elements that Guangdong private vocational college instructors consider when deciding whether to pursue postgraduate studies in Malaysia, with a focus on the management discipline. Given the worldwide nature of education and the rising allure of pursuing studies overseas, it is crucial for academic institutions and governments to understand the motives and variables considered by Guangdong private vocational college professors. This study makes use of a detailed examination of current data spans and a thorough evaluation of pertinent scholarly literature. The goal is to identify the key factors that drive Guangdong private college instructors' choices when they contemplate attending postgraduate school in Malaysia. In this work, push-pull theory and the consumer decision-making model are combined to create a complete model using structural equation modeling (SEM). The goal is to identify and investigate the important factors that influence Guangdong private vocational college instructors' decision-making when they choose private higher education schools in Malaysia. The results of this poll show that the belief that overseas education is of a higher caliber than that in their home countries is what drives most international students to pursue their education abroad. Guangdong private vocational college professors place great importance on a host nation that has a positive reputation as a study destination and presents a friendly image. When studying abroad in a nation with a good reputation, international students often feel more secure and accepted. International students are more likely to choose a nation if it has a variety of desirable characteristics, including political stability and safety, social and cultural diversity, quick processing of visas, and an adaptable immigration system. The findings of this research will significantly enhance tactics for luring and keeping Guangdong private vocational college instructors in Malaysian higher education institutions.

Keywords: Guangdong Private Vocational College Teachers, Postgraduate Study, Malaysia, Management Discipline, Decision-Making, International Education.

1. INTRODUCTION

The internationalization of higher education has witnessed a significant surge in Guangdong private vocational college teachers seeking study opportunities abroad. In recent years, Malaysia has emerged as an appealing destination for Guangdong private vocational college teachers pursuing postgraduate education due to its diverse academic programs, affordability compared to Western countries, and geographical proximity. Understanding the factors influencing Guangdong private vocational college teachers' decisions to study in Malaysia is crucial for both Malaysian universities and policymakers to develop effective recruitment strategies and enhance educational cooperation between the two countries.

Despite the awareness among the majority of higher education institutions (HEIs) regarding the imperative need for distinctive offerings in the market, numerous institutions still face challenges in formulating a comprehensive and feasible plan (Qiang, 2003). When collaborating with instructors from diverse countries and socioeconomic backgrounds in Guangdong private vocational colleges, who possess distinct requirements, preferences, and expectations, it can present a difficulty to adopt a more comprehensive perspective. This assertion holds particular significance when engaging with students hailing from diverse nations (Wilkins & Huisman, 2011). Conducting research on the primary factors that influence the decision-making process of Guangdong private vocational college teachers in selecting private higher education institutions is of utmost importance in order to develop effective marketing and differentiation strategies. This will enable individuals to develop efficacious marketing and differentiation strategies.

This assertion holds particular validity in the context of Malaysia due to its comparatively smaller population, which consequently limits the scope of the local higher education market. Therefore, it is imperative for the nation to enhance its presence in the global market by enticing international students from other countries (Cheng et al., 2013). Numerous higher education institutions (HEIs) are currently engaged in proactive exploration of potential opportunities for global collaboration. This strategic pursuit is driven by the belief that such collaborations can expand the range of educational opportunities offered by these institutions, as well as enhance their presence in both local and international markets (Cheng et al., 2013). Malaysia's higher education institutions are likely to encounter considerable obstacles in their endeavors to fulfill the newly established criteria, primarily due to the nation's delayed entry into the realm of prominent hosting countries like the United States, the United Kingdom, and Australia (Migin et al., 2015; Ahmad & Buchanan, 2016). The Malaysian government aspires to establish the country as a prominent education hub and aims to attract a substantial number of international students. By the year 2020, the government envisions enrolling 200,000 international students in its domestic Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The establishment of this target was driven by the government's objective to transform Malaysia into a prominent center for education. The objective of attaining this aspiration by the government served as the driving force behind the establishment of this goal. Nevertheless, according to the Ministry of Higher Education (2018a), recent statistical data pertaining to the enrollment of international students in Malaysian educational institutions in 2017 indicates that the country is currently not making progress towards the aforementioned objective. The observed phenomenon can be attributed primarily to a decline in the influx of students originating from Nigeria, Yemen, and Iran. Historically, these three countries have been the principal sources of international students in Malaysia, collectively contributing to nearly half of the overall foreign student population. This could potentially serve as the primary catalyst for the aforementioned alteration. Furthermore, the observed growth in the influx of international students has been relatively modest (Migin et al., 2015; Wang and Chuang 2017). In order to effectively respond to the growing competitiveness and consumer-driven nature of the higher education market, providers of higher education must undertake the task of identifying and comprehending the key factors that influence students' choices with regards to

private higher education institutions. It is imperative for higher education providers to align with market demands. This information can be utilized by higher education institutions (HEIs) to efficiently adapt their existing marketing strategies or develop new marketing plans in order to strategically position themselves in the market, as outlined in the subsequent criteria (Simic & Carapic, 2008).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Motives for Studying Abroad

The pursuit of international education presents a multitude of advantages in terms of personal growth, academic development, and professional prospects for students. Based on the findings of Wang and Chuang (2017), it is evident that Guangdong private vocational college teachers exhibit various motivations for pursuing overseas education. These include the desire to develop a global perspective, access high-quality educational opportunities, enhance language proficiency, broaden professional networks, and augment employment prospects. Moreover, Li, Bray, and Koo (2019) conducted a study which revealed that Guangdong private vocational college educators also perceive cultural exploration, personal development, and the desire to evade intense domestic competition as supplementary factors driving their motivation. In the realm of theory and research pertaining to the demand for higher education, the inclusion of student choice is a pivotal and indispensable element. Throughout the passage of time, a multitude of ideas and models have been amalgamated in order to examine the complex phenomenon of decision-making (Vrontis et al., 2007). The emergence of students' choice models can be traced back to the early 1980s. Numerous studies have been conducted to enhance our comprehension of the university selection process, which can generally be categorized into three main models: the economic model, the status attainment model, and the combined model (Hossler et al., 1999). The utilization of choice models (Kusumawati, 2013) has facilitated researchers in acquiring a more comprehensive comprehension of the intricate decision-making process involved in the selection of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This process is known to be arduous and time-consuming, as it is influenced by a diverse array of circumstances. These models are linked to a diverse range of general consumer behavior and decision-making models that are employed in research related to higher education.

2.2 Factors Influencing Guangdong Private Vocational College Teachers' Decisions

Guangdong private vocational college instructors choose postgraduate study overseas for several reasons. According to research, academic reputation, program quality, scholarship availability, cost of education, language of instruction, career chances, cultural diversity, and living environment are important (Ma, 2018; Zha, 2019). Liu, He, and Tan (2018) stress the role of social and cultural elements such parental support, peer influence, and social networks in students' study abroad choices.

The push-pull hypothesis was first used to study migration concerns (Lee, 1996) before being applied to Guangdong private vocational college teacher mobility. "The Law of Migration" by Ernst Ravenstein (1885) in the Journal of the Statistical Society founded

the push-pull hypothesis. This article argued "push and pull" dynamics regulate migration. This work started the push-pull hypothesis. Push factors are unfavorable situations that cause individuals to move to new chances. However, pull forces attract people to a new area (Dorigo & Tobler, 1983). Thus, push-pull factors influence migratory flows and their direction (Portes & Borocz, 1989).

McMahon (1992) pioneered the application of the push-pull theory to examine Guangdong private vocational college teachers in the US in the 1960s and 1970s. The push-pull paradigm has been used extensively to study international student mobility (Mazzarol & Soutar, 2002; Chen, 2007). Push considerations relate to a student's choice to study abroad due to their home country's poor status (Mazzarol & Soutar 2002; Gatfield & Chen 2006). The host country's attractiveness and institutional strengths are pull factors (Wilkins et al., 2012).

Figure 1: Push-Pull Model (Mazzarol & Soutar, 2002)

According to the push-pull theory, which is similar to other combination models, there are three steps to a student's decision-making process (see Figure 1): deciding whether to study abroad, choosing a place for that study, and deciding on a higher education institution. Both internal and external factors might have had an impact on the choice to study abroad. According to Altbach (1991) and Chen (2007), push factors often have to do with negative political and economic circumstances in the nation of origin. Select the host nation after deciding on the objective. Pull factors, a wide variety of country-specific circumstances, may make one region more alluring than another during this time. The image, culture, language, political stability, cost of living, closeness, and simplicity of obtaining a visa are examples of nation pull factors (Mazzarol & Soutar, 2002). The third part is when students choose their school. Institutions are now distinguished from one another by additional pull variables called institutional features. Pull factors are often

positive (Llewellyn-Smith & McCabe, 2008; Chen, 2007; Maringe & Carter, 2007; Mazzarol & Soutar, 2002). According to Singh et al. (2014), pull variables have a greater impact on students' judgements than push ones. Potential students may be attracted by image, reputation, quality, programs, costs, location, work opportunities, environment, and amenities.

Students' decisions to study abroad have been studied using the push-pull theory (McMahon, 1992; Mazzarol & Soutar, 2002; Maringe & Carter, 2007; Bodycott, 2009; Zheng, 2014). The push factor explains to the student's country why they choose one study place over another. To draw in local students and stop the brain drain, national governments may place a higher priority on upgrading their less desirable characteristics (Cinel, 1991; Ahmad & Buchanan, 2015). The host nation and its higher education institutions might develop a more focused international recruitment strategy by understanding what draws students. According to some researchers' expansion of the push-pull theory (Mazzarol & Soutar, 2002; Binsardi & Ekwulugo, 2003; Cheng et al., 2013), institutions should have unique pull characteristics that set them apart from competitors. According to Portes and Rumbaut (1990), the push-pull hypothesis offers a comprehensive and unwavering account of international student mobility.

2.3 The Role of Management Discipline

Management attracts Guangdong private vocational college instructors to Malaysia for postgraduate study. Zhang and Huang (2021) say management program reputation and rating, accreditation, instructor quality, internship and networking opportunities, industry connections, and alumni network are important. Guangdong private vocational college professors interested in management benefit from well-established corporate centres like Kuala Lumpur (Raghavan & Pandit, 2019). Political stability, especially safety and security, may attract international students. "Political stability" relates to how secure people feel in a country and is often linked to its public image. According to Bodycott (2009), Chinese parents often consider crime and local attitudes toward foreigners when choosing a place for their children to visit. However, Guangdong private vocational college professors did not prioritize their own safety and security as their parents did. Malaysia has a low crime rate and is politically stable (Fernandez, 2010). The Global Peace Index (2015) ranked Malaysia as the 28th most peaceful nation, bolstering its image as a safe academic destination. Malaysia's excellent grade supports its safety and tranquility. The Global Peace Index (GPI) rates each nation's peacefulness based on three factors: safety and security, internal and international conflict, and militarization. Singh et al. (2014) found that Middle Eastern students were more willing to study abroad in Malaysia due to its quiet and safe atmosphere. Kaur (2016) and Ahmad and Buchanan (2016) found that Malaysia's political and environmental stability explain its desirability as a Southeast Asian academic destination.

2.4 Cultural and Social Factors

Due to economic and cultural factors, Guangdong private vocational college lecturers study abroad. Making decisions is influenced by social networks, collectivism in China, and expectations from the family (Wang, 2017). The perceptions of Guangdong private

vocational college teachers of studying in Malaysia may also be positively influenced by the cultural affinities, parallels, and historical links between China and Malaysia (Tan, 2018). According to Cheng et al. (2013), Malaysia has a market niche advantage because of its cultural variety. Malaysia boasts a diversified student population, no discrimination, and no language barrier. These are the main factors luring foreign students to Malaysia. Islamic Malaysia draws Muslim students from various nations who want to study there. According to Singh et al. (2014), Middle Eastern students' decision to attend school in Malaysia was impacted by their religious upbringing. According to many academics (Tahar, 2014; Ahmad & Buchanan, 2015; Kaur, 2016), Malaysia's Islamic status has increased its appeal as a location for higher education. According to Kaur (2016), Malaysia attracted Guangdong private vocational college professors due to shared cultural and linguistic traits with China, Singapore, Thailand, the Middle East, and Indonesia. For Indonesian students, Malaysia's Indonesian-speaking population is a big lure. For these students, Malaysia was a fantastic learning environment because of the friendly natives and the abundance of English use (Ahmad & Buchanan, 2016).

3. METHODOLOGY

A mixed-methods approach will be used to examine Guangdong private vocational college instructors' choices to pursue postgraduate education in Malaysia. In-depth interviews with Chinese postgraduate students presently enrolled in Malaysia are part of the qualitative component. The interviews will examine the decision-making processes, driving forces, and elements that contributed to their decision to study in Malaysia. In order to collect information on the many variables affecting Chinese postgraduate students' decisions to study in Malaysia, the quantitative component will make use of a survey questionnaire that will be given to a wider sample of Chinese postgraduate students. The analysis of both primary and secondary data will provide a thorough grasp of the study issue.

McGivern (2003) asserts that it is the duty of the researcher to guarantee and show that research is carried out in a proper and ethical way. According to the rules set by Victoria University and taking into account the ethical ramifications, this research protects the respondents' right to privacy. All of the sample groups placed a high value on keeping its members' identities and confidentiality private. According to McGivern (2003)'s recommendations, ethical norms were adhered to throughout this research:

- i. Respondents were urged to participate in this survey on a voluntary basis. No student was forced to take part in the study against their will.
- ii. The researcher got permission from all participants and made sure that respondents were informed before to the survey.
- iii. The researcher made sure that any information that was submitted was handled as totally anonymous and private.
- iv. Transparency was maintained throughout this research, and participants were made aware that the information they provided would only be utilised for academic reasons. This includes not withholding anything from them, lying to them, or

engaging in any other kind of deception in order to get them to participate in the study.

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Motives for Guangdong private vocational college teachers to Study in Malaysia

Based on the literature review and analysis of the data collected, this section will present the key motives driving Guangdong private vocational college teachers to pursue postgraduate education in Malaysia. The findings will shed light on the personal, academic, and career-related factors that influence their decision-making process.

4.2 Key Factors Influencing Guangdong private vocational college teachers' Decisions

This section will identify and discuss the key factors that influence Guangdong private vocational college teachers' decisions to study in Malaysia. These factors may include academic reputation, program quality, scholarship availability, cost of education, language of instruction, employment opportunities, and cultural diversity. The findings will provide insights into the factors that attract Guangdong private vocational college teachers to choose Malaysia as their preferred study destination.

4.3 Role of Management Discipline in Decision-Making

The specific factors that influence Guangdong private vocational college teachers' decisions to pursue postgraduate education in the management discipline in Malaysia will be explored in this section. The reputation and ranking of management programs, accreditation, faculty quality, internship and networking opportunities, industry partnerships, and alumni network will be examined. The findings will highlight the significance of these factors in shaping Guangdong private vocational college teachers' decisions to study management in Malaysia.

4.4 Cultural and Social Factors Affecting Decision-Making

This section will discuss the cultural and social factors that significantly influence Guangdong private vocational college teachers' decisions to study in Malaysia. The impact of collectivism, familial expectations, social networks, and the historical ties between China and Malaysia will be explored. The findings will provide a deeper understanding of how these factors shape Guangdong private vocational college teachers' perceptions and choices.

Guangdong private vocational college professors' happiness and ambition to promote the school were examined using cross-tabulation analytic methods. The Pearson Chi-Square test showed a positive correlation between Guangdong private vocational college teachers' satisfaction and their willingness to promote the HEI ($p < 0.05$). A satisfied customer is more likely to share their experience (Arambewela & Hall, 2003; Buddhichiwin, 2013; Bianchi, 2013; Chong, 2015). Table 1 shows that 338 students (77.7%) were willing to recommend their school, whereas 41 students (9.4%) were not. 314 of 366 pleased HEI respondents (85.8%) had a positive WOM intention for the

institution. Despite considerable desire, 15 pleased respondents (4.1%) refused to promote their school. 48.8% of dissatisfied students (20 out of 41) declined to talk positively about their school. The poll found that Guangdong private vocational college professors were more likely to recommend Malaysia and their HEI the higher their satisfaction. However, decreasing pleasure lowered this willingness. Test results supported the hypothesis.

Table 1: The Cross-Tabulation Study Results for Guangdong Private Vocational College Teachers' Overall Satisfaction with Their Current Private Heis and Readiness to Promote Them to Others

			Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Total
Overall satisfaction towards HEI	Dissatisfied	Count	20	10	11	41
		% within overall satisfaction towards Malaysia	48.8%	24.4%	26.8%	100.0%
		% of Total	4.6%	2.3%	2.5%	9.4%
	Neutral	Count	6	9	13	28
		% within overall satisfaction towards Malaysia	21.4%	32.1%	46.4%	100.0%
		% of Total	1.4%	2.1%	3.0%	6.4%
	Satisfied	Count	15	37	314	366
		% within overall satisfaction towards Malaysia	4.1%	10.1%	85.8%	100.0%
		% of Total	3.4%	8.5%	72.2%	84.1%
Total		Count	41	56	338	435
		% within overall satisfaction towards Malaysia	9.4%	6.4%	84.1%	100.0%
		% of Total	9.4%	12.9%	77.7%	100.0%
Chi-Square Tests						
		Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)		
Pearson Chi-Square		117.409 ^a	4	.000		
N of Valid Cases		435				

5. IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and discussions, this section will outline the implications for Malaysian higher education institutions and provide recommendations for attracting and retaining Guangdong private vocational college teachers in the management discipline. Strategies may include enhancing academic programs, improving support services, fostering intercultural experiences, strengthening industry-academia partnerships, and expanding alumni networks. These recommendations will assist Malaysian universities in developing effective recruitment strategies to attract and retain Guangdong private vocational college teachers.

6. CONCLUSION

This research article has provided a comprehensive analysis of Guangdong private vocational college teachers' decisions to undertake postgraduate study in Malaysia, with a focus on the management discipline. By examining the motives, key factors, and cultural influences, this study has generated valuable insights for educational institutions and policymakers. The findings emphasize the need for continuous efforts to enhance the attractiveness of Malaysian universities and create a conducive environment for Guangdong private vocational college teachers' academic pursuits.

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